

The Truth about OnlyFans:

Disempowering and Unsustainable for Women's Fight for Gender Equity

Sex work has historically been morally stigmatized and regarded as disempowering for women due to its focus on male satisfaction and granting men control over women's sexuality. When Christianity first established itself as a rising influence in Medieval Europe, its strong moral belief system consequently led to the criminalization of female prostitutes and violent punishments such as flogging and forced amputation of the nose or fingers, all in an attempt to establish men's dominance over women's bodies (Bosworth 9). Similarly, with the establishment of Colonial America and expanding public moral codes regarding women's purity and modesty, prostitution was regarded as an infraction upon moral integrity – an act of subjugating women below men. Public concern regarding the morality of sex work eventually increased in such influence that the United States passed the Page Law in 1875 to ban women who participated in “lewd and immoral purposes,” thus exemplifying a legislative act that validated how sex work devalued women (Bosworth 12). Even in the 20th century with the rise of media forms such as plays and motion pictures, the public's moral panic to rescue women from the scandalization of sex work and their presumed cognitive dissonance continued to amplify in magnitude (Bosworth 14). History has framed traditional sex work as the epitome of disempowerment and immorality for women.

Yet the onset of the internet at the turn of the 21st century seemed to represent a shift in public stigmatization of sex work. With the expansion of the internet, sex workers were able to advertise their services to clients in a safer and more accessible way. In particular, social media has not only allowed sex workers to reach a wider clientele, but it also allowed them to continue their work off of the streets and free from the physical restraint of police (Bosworth 19). In

response to the digital transformation of the sex industry, various platforms began to rise to allow sex workers to make a living from producing sexually explicit content of themselves without actually having to meet with clients. Most notably, OnlyFans.com, a popular social media site where creators can charge monthly subscriptions for exclusive access to explicit content of themselves, not only transformed sex work from a traditionally face-to-face industry into a booming business of digital patronage, but it also made sex work more socially accepted in an unprecedented manner.

In the zeitgeist of body positivity, social media popularity, and financial freedom, *The Daily* journalist Katie Newman notes that a large portion of both the online community and college students have lauded OnlyFans for “destigmatizing the world of online sex work,” and the women creators themselves agree (Newman). In an interview with *Body+Soul* blog, OnlyFans content creator Lucy Banks states that being an OnlyFans content creator is “the single most empowering thing” (Green). Despite the increasing view that women OnlyFans content creators represent the epitome of women empowerment, body positivity, and self-agency, traditional attitudes toward sex work still linger. Many individuals across a range of sexual identities, ages, geographic ranges, and political affiliations continue to argue that because it is a platform in which the content creators are predominantly women while the users are predominantly men, OnlyFans objectifies women and causes them to be “perceived as subordinate, which has granted them an inferior social and political status” (Stoykova). Thus, while OnlyFans has arguably destigmatized sex work, there is still the fundamental question of whether or not it progresses women’s sovereignty. From its surface, OnlyFans seems to represent a pivot away from traditional sex work – a platform that leverages women’s sexual agency. Yet upon closer inspection, OnlyFans is rather a modern extension of the intrinsic

disempowerment of women in traditional sex work because women OnlyFans creators inevitably objectify their bodies for profit, thus continuing the subordination of women under men.

Founded by Tom Stokely in 2016, OnlyFans was imagined as “a site where fans could request videos and pornographers could satisfy their admirers’ specific fetishes” (Shaw). The “creator-fan” relationship thus serves as a prominent feature of the platform, and while Stokely envisioned OnlyFans as a way for creators to profit off of selling any type of exclusive content, it inevitably became associated with selling risqué content. The website itself situates creators as contractors and – like other gig platforms – creators give a cut of their earnings to OnlyFans: specifically 20% (“Ultimate Guide to Onlyfans.”). Yet unlike other gig economy jobs such as Uber or Lyft, OnlyFans advertises itself as a “social platform revolutionizing creator and fan connections” (*Instagram*). By emphasizing that it is “revolutionizing” the relationship between influencers and followers, OnlyFans demonstrates that it values authenticity over the superficiality that is widely present in social media. Its focus on intimacy, however, has consequently allowed OnlyFans to differentiate itself from popular social media platforms such as Instagram or Facebook in that it allows for nudity – a form of physical intimacy – and users must pay to access certain profiles or posts. From the user perspective, users can pay a monthly fee to subscribe to accounts, pay for one-time or requested content, leave tips, and send private messages; from the creator perspective, creators get to decide when they work, where they work, and the level of nudity in their content. Therefore, not only does OnlyFans allow sex workers to easily brand and monetize their image, but its simultaneous role as a gig economy platform and social media site – in combination with its lack of dictatorship over creators’ content – has contributed to its growing attractiveness as the ultimate site of women’s authority.

As sole proprietors with direct control over their economic transactions, OnlyFans content creators appear to exercise financial sovereignty. In an interview with OnlyFans creator Courtney Tillia, she reminisces upon the beginnings of her career, stating, “I always wanted to start at a higher number, so I charged \$20.99 a month” (Rella). By emphasizing the words “I charged,” Tillia claims absolute control over her content from a financial standpoint. Additionally, by stating that she “wanted to start at a higher number,” Tillia not only takes control over how much she believes her content is worth, but she separates herself to be the boss of her content, rather than integrating herself as the content. Similarly, in Karl Marx’s concept of commodity fetishism, Marx states that “the products of labor become commodities” and that the commodities “have absolutely no connection with their physical properties” (Marx 48); rather, the commodities “appear as independent beings endowed with life” (Marx 49). In other words, Marx states that under capitalism, the intrinsic value of the labor that was used to make the product is lost, and instead, the product becomes separate from the human laborer who created it. In both Rella’s situation and the general context of sex work, the content that the customer engages with becomes a commodity, which remains separate from the sex workers themselves. Therefore, Marx’s theoretical lens of commodity fetishism seems to validate the separation between the content creator – the boss – and their content – the commodity. Rella continues to elaborate upon the presumed control she has over her financial transactions, commenting, “I’ll try different things... at different prices and just see how people respond” (Rella). Again, by highlighting her ability to sell her content at “different prices,” Rella not only alludes to OnlyFans as a platform where women can adopt full control of their finances, but she also establishes a boundary between herself and her content because she can clearly control the monetary value of her content. Therefore, from the surface, OnlyFans’ gig economy platform

perfectly aligns with Marx's lens of commodity fetishism because OnlyFans creators appear as separate entities from the explicit content they create.

Yet while women OnlyFans content creators have control over setting the prices of their content, this is an incomplete representation of actual sovereignty; in fact, when considering the relationship between the content, its financial value, and how creators choose what content to make, it quickly becomes clear that the financial control that content creators appear to possess is inherently flawed. The trend of OnlyFans as the gateway to financial freedom has become popularized from documentaries such as *Nudes4Sale*. In this documentary, reporter Ellie Flynn provides the common public with deep insight into the adult entertainment industry of OnlyFans by showcasing the work life of multiple OnlyFans' Top Creators. At first glance, this documentary showcases OnlyFans as an enticing financial opportunity for influencers to take advantage of, emphasizing how creator Lauren Elizabeth earns "nearly thirty-five grand a month" by being her own boss and controlling the pricing of her content (*Nudes4Sale*, 3:15-3:18). By immediately establishing the monetary appeal of OnlyFans through glamorizing how Elizabeth earns "thirty-five grand a month" – an undoubtedly high profit – *Nudes4Sale* affirms that money is the driving motivational factor for these content creators. Nevertheless, it quickly becomes apparent that this financial freedom comes at the cost of the creators' freedom of choice. Sasha, another OnlyFans Top Creator, states, "I'm not going to put a photo of me... in my pajamas...because that's not going to get me anything. So they're only seeing the good things." (*Nudes4Sale*, 31:22-31:30). Sasha's remark that she doesn't post content "that's not going to get [her] anything" conveys how OnlyFans creators feel pressured to post the type of content that brings them greater profit, thus carving a toxic hole in which the creators are not in complete control of their content and money. Rather, they are subject to the appeal of money and,

consequently, coerced to create content that will allow them to gain that money . The restriction of content conferred by financial strategy ultimately leads to the creators' own commodification. This aligns with late 20th-century feminist theorist Catherine Mackinnon, who notes that sex work inherently fails to cultivate women's sovereignty because it "sells women to men as and for sex" (Mackinnon 195). Therefore, while women OnlyFans content creators exercise dominance over the pricing of their content, this financial control is not women's sovereignty; the financial appeal that drives women OnlyFans content creators results in the women "selling" themselves to men by subjecting themselves to men's content demands.

Although the capitalistic nature of OnlyFans inevitably results in the pressure of financial strategy that dictates the level of risqué content that women creators post, OnlyFans does seem to represent an improvement from the lack of women's agency in traditional pornography because OnlyFans women creators not only have control over their medium in the sense that they are responsible for the content they create, but they also exercise control over their role within their content. OnlyFans creator Aella Stoyam, for example, states in an interview with *GQ's Modern Lovers* that traditional sex work causes "a lot of girls to be beholden to emotionally abusive members," but in contrast, since OnlyFans content mainly exhibits solo work, "OnlyFans feels like it's really put the power in the hands of the performers themselves" (Nast). Through contrasting the "emotionally abusive" power dynamic of traditional sex work with how OnlyFans "really put the power in the hands of the performers," Stoyam demonstrates how some creators believe that OnlyFans is transforming the sex industry by allocating sexual power in the female creator rather than a male creator. In other words, women creators are the sole directors of their content. In addition to having agency over their medium, OnlyFans women content creators appear to also possess control over what they perform in their content. In *Nudes4Sale*, Lauren

Elizabeth performs various solo poses in front of the camera, laying on the floor and arching her back in order to emphasize the curvature of her breasts and bottom (*Nudes4Sale*, 1:51-2:01). At first glance, Lauren takes agency in her own body and sexuality, and the lack of a male counterpart further emphasizes her sovereignty in this form of sex work – a traditionally heterosexual concept. In Laura Mulvey’s “Visual Pleasure,” she states that in film, the “passive/female” is sexualized by an “active/male,” and as a result, spectators identify themselves with the active male figure that projects his exhibitionist gaze onto women, leading them to internalize women as sexual objects of pleasure (Mulvey 19). While Mulvey’s concept directly applies to traditional pornography which exhibits both a man and woman on screen, this idea breaks down in OnlyFans due to the woman creator’s agency over the role she performs in her content. The absence of an “active/male” to dictate what OnlyFans women creators can do in their content seems to suggest that spectators cannot identify themselves with a male figure and, therefore, the woman creator’s sovereignty is not lost to the exhibitionist gaze of men.

Nevertheless, despite the lack of an “active/male” in Lauren’s content, Lauren does not weaponize her figure, but poses in a way that sexualizes the features that appeal to the male gaze. Lauren directly faces the camera, using her arms to emphasize her breasts and tilting her head to highlight her seductive eyes (*Nudes4Sale*, 2:26-2:30). The photos Lauren takes are consequently uploaded to her OnlyFans profile, where male users view her body from the camera’s perspective. By directing the camera to her enhanced breasts and wide eyes, Lauren forces her male subscribers to take on an exhibitionist gaze; yet instead of identifying themselves with an active male figure, the spectators identify themselves with the camera – an even more direct form of voyeurism than indirectly projecting their gaze through a male counterpart. Similarly, OnlyFans creator Sasha poses with an eye mask as she holds the phone camera at an upward

angle, moving her hair aside in order to grasp a fuller view of her breasts (*Nudes4Sale*, 31:26-31:31). By holding the camera at an angle above her, Sasha physically situates herself below the viewer – creating an imbalance of power in which she remains submissive to the lens of the camera. Furthermore, by covering her facial features with an eye mask and moving her hair aside from her breasts, Sasha is clearly directing attention to the curvature of her breasts – thus further sexualizing her features that appeal to the male gaze. Despite the lack of a male counterpart, both Lauren and Sasha continue to force spectators into voyeuristic tendencies through the perspective of the camera. Therefore, while Mulvey’s claim that spectators can only objectify women through identifying with an active male figure fails to take into account the ability to identify with the camera itself, we can still extend Mulvey’s concept of voyeurism to the “passive/female” content creator and the “active/male” camera. Ultimately, OnlyFans content creators fail to claim sexual agency through their solo work, as their intention of sexualizing their body for the camera – and thus the male spectator – inevitably results in a heterosexual dynamic in which the spectator possesses a dominant, exhibitionist gaze over the submissive woman creator, allowing the spectator to internalize women as sexual objects.

OnlyFans fails to resolve the agential aspect of women’s sovereignty, instead masking its void with financial compensation. Yet, the creators themselves still view OnlyFans as life-changing from an individual scale due to its ability to confer sovereignty of choice outside of the platform. Creator Bayden Bauer comments in an interview with *GQ’s Modern Love* that before joining OnlyFans, she would question her financial decisions “even when [she] would buy food,” but since becoming a creator, OnlyFans allowed her to “put some money aside for taxes and music and still be able to do whatever [she] wanted” (Nast). It appears that since Bauer is now “able to do whatever [she] wanted,” the financial compensation conferred by OnlyFans has

alleviated Bauer's anxiety over her finances – thus, granting her both financial and mental freedom outside of OnlyFans. In the same interview, creator Sarvani boasts that OnlyFans allowed her “to move into [her] dream house at 22” (Nast). Once again, OnlyFans allowed Sarvani to strike rich, consequently allowing her to move out and live an independent, financially-stable life. Thus, at an individual level, OnlyFans does confer sovereignty in certain aspects – particularly sovereignty over financial choices outside of the platform as a result of the profit generated by the creator's content and subscribers.

Nevertheless, individuals must not let the prospect of sovereignty of choices mask them from realizing that short-term sovereignty from an individual scale fails to progress long-term sovereignty from a societal scale. This form of neoliberal feminism, which presents “the struggle for gender equality as now largely down to the individual,” ultimately downplays women's inequality at a structural level by subsuming it to an individual level that emphasizes gender equality through “personal improvement” (Sitkin). Yet, by narrowing the scope of the fight for gender equity “largely down to the individual,” and thus intertwining feminism with capitalism, we not only fail to address gender equality for society as a whole, but we also fail to adopt a sustainable approach to feminism for future generations. At its root, OnlyFans still intrinsically capitalizes upon male objectification of women. If creators continue to normalize OnlyFans as a platform to achieve sovereignty of choices in their real life, they are indirectly normalizing a platform that restricts women's sovereignty from an agential aspect; this systemization does not remove the harm but rather makes it even harder to address.

Obtaining full sovereignty for women thus requires a utilitarian mindset – one that critiques neoliberal feminism. In other words, in order to prevent the hypersexualization and devaluation of women, women must put the interests of future generations of women before their

individual interests; this means not capitulating to the enticing prospect that being an OnlyFans creator could allow them to gain sovereignty of financial choices outside of the platform. Thus, we must not only dismantle OnlyFans but ignite conversation on how to both reduce the financial attractiveness of the online gig industry and expand the scope of feminism from the individual level to a societal level. First, we must leverage social media to rally online users to critique the unsustainability of neoliberal feminism. Consequently, we can encourage these online users to support restricting access to sources that authorize sexual voyeurism of women by men and – therefore – minimize the sexual imbalance of power. By taking these first key actions, we can ultimately reduce the attractiveness of online sex work and move one step closer to achieving a form of complete sovereignty for women that is free from the constraint of the male gaze.

Despite the presumed capability of OnlyFans to transform traditional sex work by promoting women's control over their role in sex work, pricing of their content, and financial choices outside of the platform, OnlyFans veritably serves as an extension of traditional sex work and an instrument that restricts women's agency. Only through critiquing this form of neoliberal feminism and reducing the financial attractiveness of the online gig industry will we be able to limit access to sources that authorize sexual voyeurism of women, minimize their sovereignty, and systematize their commodification. Understanding the intrinsic effects of online sex work on public behavior and the intersectionality between capitalism, heterosexual dynamics, and their resulting effect on human psychology is necessary to subvert subordination of women and fight for gender equity.

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